

EXPLORING NUTRITIONAL AND THERAPEUTIC EFFICACY OF AMLA, CURRY LEAVES, AND GINGER: A HOLISTIC REVIEW

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Abstract

Amla, curry leaves, and ginger are traditional medicinal plants known for their rich nutritional and therapeutic value. They are abundant in antioxidants, vitamins, and bioactive compounds, offering benefits such as anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, and cardioprotective effects. This study highlights their taxonomy, morphology, chemical composition, therapeutic properties, drying techniques, and sensory characteristics, emphasizing their significance in health promotion, disease prevention, and potential as functional ingredients in food and pharmaceutical applications.

Keywords: Antioxidants, Drying techniques, Phytochemicals.

Introduction

Amla

The Indian gooseberry, or amla (*Emblica officinalis*), is a significant fruit crop that is grown throughout the Indian subcontinent. Because of its medicinal properties, it is frequently utilized in Ayurvedic and Unani systems. One of the best sources of vitamin C is amla, which has roughly 20 and 160 times more vitamin C than an orange or an apple, respectively. Fresh Amla has a short shelf life and a sour, strong astringent flavour, which limits its use. As a result, it is used in many processed forms, with dehydrated powder being the most popular [62].

In Indian pharmacopoeia, amla is regarded as a potent rejuvenator plant and one of the best suppliers of ascorbic acid (500 – 1,500g/100g). Amla has a positive impact on lowering blood cholesterol levels. Chronic dysentery, bronchitis, diabetes, cancer, fever, diarrhoea, jaundice, dyspepsia, coughs, and other conditions are also treated with it. Fresh Amla fruit has the greatest ascorbic acid level of any fruit, net of Barbados cherries, with 950 mg/100 g. While the two drying procedures have a substantial impact on the dried amla product, solar drying produced a higher ascorbic acid content (285.2 mg/100g). It is well-known for its medicinal properties and is a rich source of vitamin C, antioxidants, polyphenols, tannins, and minerals [21].

Taxonomy

Table 1

Kingdom	<i>Plantae</i>
Division	Angiospermae
Class	Dicotyledonae
Order	Geraniales
Family	Euphorbiaceae
Genus	<i>Emblica</i>
Species	<i>Officinalis</i> Geartn

(Source: Kulkarni and Ghurghure 2018)

Morphology

In India, *Embllica officinalis* is grown extensively. Other closely related species, such as *Embllica myrobalan*, which has medium-sized to relatively small foliage, are included. The pickle-making plant *Embllica fischeri* and the wide-crowned tree *Phyllanthus indofischeri* are both found in the scrub woods of south India. Most of these species are cultivated for their aesthetic qualities [9]. The euphorbiaceae family includes *Phyllanthus embllica Linn*, and it is widely found in most tropical and subtropical countries. The fruits, flowers, seeds, leaves, and bark of *Phyllanthus Embllica* have all been widely used in a variety of traditional medicine. According to pharmacological research, *P. embllica* possesses anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, immunomodulatory, anti-viral, anti-jaundice, anti-dyslipidemic, anti-aging, anti-apoptotic, hepatoprotective, nephroprotective, and anti-diabetic properties [49].

Amla fruit has an almost spherical shape, measuring 18 to 25 mm in width. The fruit's pericarp, or mesocarp, has 15 layers and is yellow in hue, while the endocarp turns yellowish-brown when it ripens. The 20 mm-long mesocarp of fresh Amla fruit has a sour taste, but in dried fruit, it imparts a puckery flavor [26].

Curry Leaves

Murraya koenigii (L.) Spreng. (Family: Rutaceae), also referred to as Meetha neem, is a fragrant, deciduous shrub or small tree that can grow up to 6 meters in height. It can be found all over India, up to 1500 meters above sea level, and is grown for its fragrant leaves. Its family includes about 150 genera and 1600 species worldwide. It is widely distributed over the outer Himalayas, Assam, the Andaman Islands, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, and the forests of Karnataka's Western Ghats [36].

Curry leaves (*Murraya koenigii*), renowned for their fragrant flavor, have long been an integral part of Indian cooking. In addition to their culinary appeal, these leaves are now gaining recognition for their potential to influence metabolic pathways [35]. Curry leaves yield essential oils, which are frequently used as seasonings in cooking. Curry leaves also include antioxidants, antimicrobials, and antibacterial qualities. One of the most crucial roles of the curry plant's leaves is to serve as the site of photosynthesis. Because different leaves have varying capacities to create reduced carbon in order to produce plant biomass, variations in leaf size have an impact on plant growth. Consequently, it is possible to use leaf development as the primary metric in plant growth study [68].

Taxonomy

Table 2

Kingdom	Plantae
Subkingdom	Tracheobionta
Superdivision	Spermatophyta
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Magnoliopsida
Order	Sapindales
Family	Rutaceae
Genus	<i>Murraya</i>
Species	<i>Murraya koenigii</i>

[61]

Morphology

Murraya koenigii is a tiny, fragrant, deciduous shrub that grows to a height of roughly 6 to 9 meters at an elevation of 1500 meters above sea level. Several spots on the main stem's dark green to brown bark can be flaking off lengthwise to reveal the white wood underneath. The leathery, glandular, 15–30 cm long, bipinnately compound leaves support 11–25 leaflets. The leaves have a weakly aromatic, somewhat acidic, and bitter flavour [13]. Curry leaves feature long stalks with an odd number of leaves (11–21), are compound leaves with a pinnate structure, and are smaller than bay leaves. The millimeter column method is one of the quick and accurate measurement methods required for leaf growth [68].

Ginger

One of the most significant spices is ginger, or *Zingiber officinale* as it is known in science. Curcuma oil, a light-yellow liquid extracted from rhizomes, has a strong, fragrant scent that makes it valuable [37]. Ginger has been shown to have pharmacological activity against radiation-induced, chemical, and natural toxicities. Its molecular mechanism of action has been studied, and it has been shown to have neuroprotective, gastroprotective, nephroprotective, hepatoprotective, and radioprotective effects [32].

Zingiber officinale A monocotyledonous rhizomatous plant, roscoe (culinary ginger) is a member of the Zingiberaceae family. It is a significant economic species that has been grown and used all over the world for centuries as a spice and medicinal in China and India [39]. Originally from South-East Asia, ginger of commerce is the subterranean rhizome of *Zingiber officinale* Rosc., a member of the Zingiberaceae family. It has been grown in Tropical Asia for more than 3,000 years, making it one of the most significant and ancient spices [4]. The culinary ginger, or *Zingiber officinale* Roscoe, is a rhizomatous, monocotyledonous plant that is a member of the Zingiberaceae family. It is a significant commercial species that is grown and used all over the world. It was first used as a spice and medicinal in ancient China and India [39].

Taxonomy

Table 3

Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Liliopsida
Order	Zingiberales
Family	Zingiberaceae
Genus	Zingiber
Species	Zingiberofficinale Roscoe

[60]

Morphology

The monocotyledonous herb *Zingiber officinale* is native to the moist tropical region. Grass-like leaves up to one foot long, this perennial herb grows to a height of two to four feet. Its underground rhizome is utilized in both medicine and cooking [37]. Ginger has a yellowish green color and a fragrant, spicy, pungent, and bitter flavor. Ginger plants can reach a height of one meter. Its leaves range in length from 6 to 12 inches. The terminal spikes of ginger blooms have a green-purple hue. Ginger's rhizomes have a buff hue [25].

The tuberous, thick, fleshy rhizome has distinct nodes and internodes, as well as scaly leaves at the nodes; it is pale yellowish-buff in color and has a distinct, pleasant aroma with a sharp, pungent taste; it branches sympodially, and the branched pieces, also called hands or races, are roughly 5–15 cm long and 1.5–6.5 cm wide; its surface is smooth, longitudinally striated, and somewhat fibrous; it is laterally compressed, bearing short, ovate, and oblique branches on the upper side, each with a depressed scar at the apex; The transverse section's lens view reveals a thin cortex, a prominent endodermis, and a broad stele with numerous, dispersed, greyish fibro-vascular bundles and yellow secreting cells. The cortex also exhibits comparable bundles [53].

Nutritional Composition

Amla

High moisture content (82.76 g/100 gm), protein (6.04 gm/100 gm), fiber (2.78 gm/100 gm), ash (2.3%/100 g), fat (0.51 gm/100 gm), and carbohydrates (82.91 gm/100 gm) are all present in amla fruit [59]. Amla fruits, which contain more than 70g of carbs per 100g of dry weight (DW), are a significant source. Other important components include fiber (7.2–16.5g/100g DW), protein, and minerals (iron, calcium, and phosphorous) as well as fat (2.0–4.5, 2.1–3.1, and 0.2–0.6g/100g DW, respectively) [24].

The fruit of *E. officinalis*, also known as amla, is consistently the highest known normal source of vitamin C (200–900 mg/100 g of edible component). A single fruit has the same antiscorbutic benefit as at least one or two oranges, and the fruit juice contains about thirty times as much vitamin C as orange juice. Similar to calcium, phosphorus, iron, niacin, carotene, thiamine, riboflavin, and nicotinic acid, it also includes minerals and amino acids [30].

Curry Leaves

Minerals, vitamins, carbs, proteins, and fatty acids are all part of the plant's nutritional potential. The amino acids lysine (5.32 g/100 g), alanine (4.17 g/100 g), methionine (1.17 g/100 g), phenylalanine (4.73 g/100 g), and crude protein (25.67 g/100 g) are all present in good amounts in it [38]. According to [43] the nutrients value per 100 grams of fresh and dry curry leaves were found out to be protein as 6g and 12g ; fat as 1g and 5.4g; carbohydrate as 18.7g and 64.31g; calcium as 830mg and 2040mg; iron as 0.93mg and 12mg; B-carotene as 0.0031mg and 0.0059mg respectively. [66] states the nutritional value of dried curry leaves powder per 100gm moisture – 5.86gm; total ash – 9.68gm; crude fibre – 5.22gm; total fat – 2.43gm; total protein – 3.81gm; total carbohydrate – 60.24gm.

Ginger

[63] reported that the proximate analysis of ginger ranges from 12.60-12.80%; 10.80-13.90% and 3.50-8.20% for crude protein; crude fibre and ash respectively. It is given in (Ogbuewu et al. 2022) that the determined proximate composition of ginger rhizome powder is 6.32 ± 0.35 for moisture; 5.45 ± 0.46 for crude protein; 6.57 ± 0.18 for ash; 10.36 ± 0.67 for crude fibre.

Chemical Composition

Amla

Amla juice has the greatest concentration of vitamin C (478.56 mg/100 ml). Numerous healthy substances were extracted from it, including isostrictiniin, ellagic acid, gallic acid, corilagin, chebulinic acid, 1,6-di-O-galloyl beta-D glucose, 3,6-di-O-galloyl-glucose, 3-ethylgallic acid (3 ethoxy 4,5 dihydroxy benzoic acid), 1-O-galloyl-beta-D-glucose, chebulagic acid, and quercetin. Furthermore, it contains a few flavonoids, such as

rhamnopyranoside 3 O alpha L (6 "methyl) and kaempferol 3 O alpha L (6 "ethyl) kaempferol [28].

Amla's medicinal uses are increased by the higher concentrations of its chemical constituents, such as ascorbic acid (478.56 mg/100 gm), phytate (49.34 mg/100 gm), gallic acid (1.32% per 100 gm), quercetin (1.26 mg/100 gm), thiamine (0.03 mg/100 gm), and riboflavin (0.03 mg/100 gm) [59]. "Phyllembin" is the active component in amla that gives it its remarkable pharmacological effect, according to Indian experts. In addition to polyphenolic chemicals like quercetin and phyllaemblic compounds, the fruit is rich in vitamin C, pectin, tannins, flavonoids, gallic acid, and flavonoids [6].

Phenolic components such as gallic acid, L-malic acid 2-o-gallate, corilagin chebulagic acid, putrajivain A, elacocarpusin, mucic acid, 1-o-galloyl- β -D-glucose, mucic acid 2-o-gallate, mucic acid 6-methyl ester 2-o-gallate, mucic acid 1,4-lactone 2-o-gallate, and others were discovered to be present in the fruit juice of *E. officinalis* [34].

Curry Leaves

Curry leaves are a rich source of many carbazole alkaloids due to their complicated chemical makeup. It has been reported that chemicals like alkaloids, flavonoids, and sterols are present in plant extracts that researchers have prepared using solvents including ethyl acetate, ethanol, petroleum ether, water, and chloroform [40]. The antioxidant and anticancer properties of *M. Koenigii*'s non-alkaloidal substances included epicatechin, catechin, quercetin, naringin, myricetin, and rutin. The antioxidant capacity of *M. Koenigii* is additionally enhanced by ferulic, gallic, vanillic, and acidic substances. In addition to trace amounts of iron, zinc, manganese, and selenium, curry leaves were rich in calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, and potassium [1]. According to [17] some of the important phytochemicals that are found in curry leaves are

- **Carotenoids:** Curry leaves contain important amounts of carotenoids, including lutein, zeaxanthin, and beta-carotene.
- **Phenolic Compounds:** The phenolic chemicals quercetin, kaempferol, and rutin are abundant in curry leaves. Compounds that are high in anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, and antioxidant components are what keep you healthy generally and shield your body against a few illnesses.
- **Flavonoids:** They consist of substances like luteolin, myricetin, and apigenin. Flavonoids have anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, and antioxidant properties.
- **Alkaloids:** Curry leaves include alkaloids such as mahanine and murrayanine. Numerous pharmacological properties, including antibacterial, antifungal, and anti-inflammatory properties, are linked to alkaloids.

Curry leaves include a variety of phytochemicals, including as terpenoid, alkaloids, flavonoids, and tannins. Antimicrobial and antioxidant properties have been documented for a few bioactive compounds, including mahanimbilyl acetate, girinimbilyl acetate, and bicyclomahanimbiline [33]. A number of chemical elements of various carbazole alkaloids and other significant metabolites, including terpenoids, flavonoids, phenolics, carbohydrates, carotenoids, vitamins, and nicotinic acid, have been linked to the therapeutic qualities of *M. Koenigii* [11].

Ginger

Ginger's components, including monoterpenes (cineole, citral, limonene, and α/β -pinenes), sesquiterpenes (β -elemene, farnesene, and zerumbone), phenolics (gingeols, [6]-shogaol, [6]-paradol, and zingerone), and diarylheptanoids (curcumin), have been shown to have biological effects (Kiyama, 2020). Terpenoids and phenolics are two of the many active substances found in ginger. Phenolic components found in ginger include paradol, zingerone, gingerol, and shogaol. Gingerols are the main polyphenols found in fresh ginger [10].

The main chemical components in ginger are: Bisabolene, zingiberene (6%) and volatile oils (1–2%). Oleo-resin, gingerol, gingerone, a ketone and aliphatic aldehyde, lipids (1–2%), A, B3 (niacin), B6 (riboflavin), and C are vitamins. Minerals: potassium, phosphorus, magnesium, and calcium. Gingerol, an alcoholic component of the oleoresin, accounts for 5–8% of ginger's pungency. Bisabolene, zingiberene, and zingiberol are the volatile oils (1–2%) that give ginger its distinctive odor [57]. Ginger's low molecular weight volatile constituents (GC/MS, GC-FID, LC/MS, HPLC) as well as monoterpenoids and sesquiterpenoids (β -bisabolene, α -zingiberene) are detected and identified using various chromatographic analyses. The primary substance in ginger that gives it its acidity is called gingerols. Heat transforms gingerols into shogaols, which give ginger its distinctively sweet and spicy odour [55].

Therapeutic Uses of Amla

- **Eye Disorder**

E. officinalis and its tannoids are used to treat eye disease because they reversed changes related to lipid peroxidation, protein carbonyl content, and the functions of antioxidant enzymes, hence reducing the likelihood of oxidative pressure. Additionally, Amla stopped the lens proteins from aggregating and becoming insolubilized due to hyperglycemia [54].

- **Anti-Cancer properties**

Phyllanthus emblica is also referred to as an anti-neoplastic agent because certain of its bioactive components, like gallic acid and phenolic compounds, prevent the growth of cancerous or neoplastic cells. When we ingest enough amla, it produces gallic acid, which inhibits the growth of prostate cancer and delays the progression of adenocarcinoma to an advanced stage. Gallic acid inhibited the growth of lung tumors as well [44].

- **Impact in Cholesterol level**

Amalaki is sympathetic to the circulatory system. Research has indicated that amalaki can lower cholesterol and serum LDH levels as well as lessen artery-clogging fat deposits, protecting the heart and arteries. Raw amalaki fruit was administered to both normal and hypercholesterolemic males for 28 days in a clinical investigation, and both groups showed a reduction in total serum cholesterol levels [29].

- **Anti-Ulcerative properties**

Emblica officinalis methanolic extract was investigated for its ability to prevent ulcers. Due to its impact on both offensive and defensive mucosal elements, *Emblica officinalis* demonstrated notable ulcer protection and healing properties [20].

- **Impedes constipation**

Constipation, or the irregular and infrequent evacuation of the intestines, can be controlled by taking one teaspoon of amla powder with milk or water each morning. However, this infection may be treated with a tea spoonful of fresh amla juice and three teaspoons of honey combined with water. Any parasitic worms causing constipation can be cured by consuming 20 grams of fresh amla juice daily [42].

- **A Potent Source of Vitamin C and Used to Prevent Scurvy and Jaundice**

Amla contains ellagic acid, a potent antioxidant that helps prevent gene mutations and correct chromosomal abnormalities. Being a very high source of vitamin C, amla, also known as Indian gooseberry, is one of the finest treatments for scurvy. Scurvy can be avoided by taking powdered dry herb three times a day with milk, combined with an equal amount of

sugar. A natural remedy for preventing scurvy and jaundice outbreaks is to drink amla juice first thing in the morning on an empty stomach [22].

- **Neurological function**

The mitigation of neurological modifications, especially the biochemical changes seen in Alzheimer's disease carriers, is one of the possible protective benefits linked to the bioactive molecule amla. Additionally, certain potential antidepressant mechanisms of action linked to amla polyphenols are indicated [24].

- **Anti-anemic effect**

Indian gooseberry, also known as amla, is an effective way to absorb iron. Amla contains a lot of vitamin C, also known as ascorbic acid, which helps to lessen iron deficiency [16].

Therapeutic Uses of Curry Leaves

Curry leaf extract contained 23.73% alkaloids. Among the secondary metabolic substances that plants make are alkaloids. Alkaloids provide several health benefits, such as raising blood pressure, acting as a nervous system trigger, lowering pain, acting as an antibiotic, acting as a sedative, treating cardiac disease, and more [8].

- **As hair growth promoter**

Since curry leaves are rich in protein and beta-carotene, these nutrients are essential for preventing hair loss and thinning. Since proteins are the building blocks of hair, they are also essential for hair growth. Additionally, curry leaves are high in amino acids, which fortify hair fiber [40].

- **Antidiabetic property**

Diabetes is a common condition throughout the world and is linked to retinopathy, nephropathy, and atherosclerosis. In several herbal medicine systems, curry leaves have long been used as a possible ingredient to cure diabetes. Mahanimbine, curry leaves' main bioactive ingredient, lowers blood sugar levels and has strong anti-diabetic effects [64].

- **Antioxidant Activity**

Despite the existence and effectiveness of antioxidant defense systems such as enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants, unrestrained ROS accumulation throughout the course of a person's lifespan promotes the emergence of age-dependent diseases including cancer, atherosclerosis, arthritis, etc. Plant-based natural antioxidants have been considered as a potential treatment for several ailments, the most common being cancer, heart disease, and neurological conditions [15].

The literature states that the antioxidative properties of the leaf extract from *Murraya koenigii* were investigated using a variety of solvents. Natural antioxidants obtained from plants have been promoted as a promising treatment and preventative measure for a number of diseases, including neurological disorders, cancer, cardiovascular disease, and other illnesses [46].

- **Potential uses of curry leaves for high cholesterol**

In an animal study, curry leaves significantly reduced the levels of triglycerides (fat) and total cholesterol. Curry leaves may lower cholesterol and fat metabolism, which is known as a hypolipidemic (lipid-lowering) action. It might aid in lowering bad cholesterol and low density lipids. Curry leaves have the benefit of lowering cholesterol levels in the body [37].

- **Anti-cancer properties**

Curry leaves have the ability to prevent mutagenesis. They protect our bodies from several types of cancer. Curry leaves contain flavonoids, which have anti-cancer properties. They are known to stop breast cancer cells from growing. Curry leaves also shield the body from colon cancer. Curry leaves also aid in preventing cervical cancer from developing in the body [17].

- **Prevents anemia**

Anemia is the result of the body's iron shortage. Curry leaves, which are rich in iron, are a very good way to raise the blood's hemoglobin and red blood cell counts. It decreases fatigue symptoms, lowers the risk of infection, and functions as a natural blood purifier [47].

- **Kidney protective**

More people are becoming aware of curry leaves' incredible ability to protect kidneys. Numerous studies have demonstrated the inherent kidney-protective properties of curry leaves. Curry leaves contain a variety of bioactive chemicals, such as alkaloids, phenolic compounds, and flavonoids, which are often credited with these advantages. These bioactive ingredients have potent anti-inflammatory and antioxidant qualities, which are critical for shielding kidney function from a range of threats [41].

Therapeutic Uses of Ginger

- **Anti-carcinogenic property**

Studies were conducted both in vitro and in vivo to assess ginger's cytotoxic effects and mode of action against prostate cancer. By suppressing the expression of MRP1 (multi-drug resistance-associated protein 1) and GST (glutathione-S-transferase), 6-gingerol, 6-shogaol, and 10-gingerol were found to have significant anti-proliferative effects on human prostate cancer cells [58].

- **Effect of Ginger on Inflammatory Diseases**

By suppressing nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B), TNF-, Nod-like receptor family proteins (NLRP), TLR, signal transducer of activators of transcription (STAT), mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK), and mTOR pathways, as well as by blocking a number of proinflammatory cytokines (IL-1, I L-6), and myeloperoxidase enzyme (MPO), ginger reduces the inflammatory response in IBD [12].

- **Antioxidant properties**

The antioxidant potential of ginger have also been disclosed by other authors. The substituent on these compounds' alkyl chain may have both a radical scavenging action and an inhibitory effect on the peroxidation of liposomes caused by peroxy radicals. The scavenging of radicals may be the cause of the antioxidant action. Strong antioxidant activity has been demonstrated for [6]-gingerol in both in vitro and in vivo settings [48].

It was discovered that ginger and gingerol, or their derivatives, had a good cleaning impact on hydroxyl radicals and superoxide anions. The pharmacological activities of other ginger derivatives, including oleoresin, 6-shogaol, 6-dehydroshogaol, 1-dehydro-6-gingerdione, 6-gingerol, 8-gingerol, 10-gingerol, and essential oils, include antimicrobial, antioxidant, and other effects on hydroxyl radicals, microbial strains [18].

- **Anti-diabetic properties**

There have been claims that ginger offers anti-diabetic qualities. The effects of ginger rhizome aqueous extracts (5, 10, 20, and 40 g/L) on glucose diffusion and protein glycation were investigated. The findings demonstrated that the extract can lessen diabetes by reducing glycation and inhibiting glucose transport [65].

- **Anti-cancer properties**

Many studies have examined ginger and its different bioactive compounds, which have been shown to have cancer-preventive and maybe cancer-therapeutic uses. Ginger contains components that have anti-inflammatory and anti-tumorigenic properties, including 6-gingerol, 6-shogaol, 6-paradol, and zerumbone. Studies on a range of cancer types, such as lymphoma, hepatoma, colorectal, breast, skin, liver, and bladder cancer, have examined the potential of ginger to prevent or slow the growth of cancer [31].

Additionally, ginger and its components can prevent pancreatic cancer. According to studies, 6-gingerol, regardless of p53 status, stops the growth of HPAC and BxPC-3 cells that cause pancreatic cancer by causing cell cycle arrest at the G1 phase. Additionally, they discovered that 6-gingerol inhibited the production of cyclin A and cyclin dependent kinase (Cdk), which in turn reduced retinoblastoma (Rb) phosphorylation and blocked S phase entry [50].

- **Anti-inflammatory properties**

In various nations, ginger and its compounds improve the immune system. The mechanism of action of gingerol, shogaol, and other structurally related chemicals in ginger is to reduce the formation of prostaglandin and leukotrienes by inhibiting 5 lipoxygenase or prostaglandin synthetase. They can also stop the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines such TNF- α , IL-1, and IL-8 [60].

- **Anti-obesity properties**

Obesity increases the risk of a number of chronic conditions, such as diabetes, hypertension, and cardiovascular disorders. Numerous studies have shown that ginger can help prevent and manage obesity. In 3T3-L1 preadipocyte cells, gingerenone A showed a more potent inhibitory effect on adipogenesis and lipid accumulation than did gingerols and 6 shogaol [19].

Drying Techniques

Cabinet drying

Compared to other drying methods, cabinet drying is more user-friendly, cost-effective, and time-efficient while maintaining the product's highest nutritional content. The types of dryers and how they are used determine the quality of the dried goods [5].

By bringing the moisture content down to a safe storage level, drying is one of the most important preservation techniques. Rapid and efficient drying methods that can minimize nutrient loss have drawn a lot of attention. Lower-temperature cabinet drying has been recommended as a suitable technology because it requires little financial outlay. Cabinet drying is a straightforward and useful approach that is preferred because it has the lowest processing costs and speeds. However, the product's color, flavor, and nutritional value may suffer as a result of this procedure [56].

Drying can add value, facilitate transport and extend the storage life of agro-products; therefore, in developing countries with poorly established cool-chains, drying is particularly effective [51].

Drying is primarily used to extend a product's shelf life, reduce bulk weight, and minimize packaging needs. By reducing or halting the growth of microbes and averting specific biochemical reactions that could change the organoleptic properties, the drying process extends the shelf life [52].

A single layer of pretreated samples was placed on the trays. When the sample reached equilibrium moisture content that is, when three consecutive moisture content readings were the same and no more moisture could be removed at the specific drying temperature—the drying process was said to be finished [14].

The Tray Dryer (TD-12-S-E), an electric heating model with 6 KW of power and a temperature of 200°C, was utilized to dry the aonla slices. The tray dryer's air velocity ranges from 0.3 to 2.3 m/s. basically a cabinet with perforated stainless steel trays holding the stuff to be dried. The dryer's primary components are the temperature controller, fan, and thermostat. There are twelve trays in the tray drier, arranged one above the other. The drying conditions are easily adjustable and controllable [7].

The aforementioned drawbacks can be mostly mitigated by cabinet tray drying because it is comparatively quick, more hygienic, and provides consistent drying. Similarly, when various Amla cultivars were dried via cabinet drying (without any treatment), a decrease in the ascorbic acid level was observed [62].

Shade drying

Drying reduces the volume and weight of raw materials, making it the most effective way to preserve fruits, vegetables, and herbs. This reduces food waste by increasing product shelf life and enabling less expensive shipping. In order to evaporate and mobilize the moisture content within the porous goods, drying requires the use of energy. Mass transfer and heat transfer take place at the same time during this procedure [67].

The conventional shadow drying method uses natural climatic changes to capture wind energy and regulate the shed's interior temperature rather without adding any extra heat sources. A sunshine plate covers the semi-circular arc at the top of the sunshade ventilation canopy. Additionally, a sunlight plate is used to seal the top semi-arcs at the front and back exits [23].

Sun drying

Drying outside In Turkey and around the world, the sun is the primary means of preserving agricultural produce. The drying process is dependent on the weather. Contamination from dust, soil, sand, and insects is an issue with this procedure. It takes a long time to dry [45].

According to the study, *H. cannabinus* that was sun-dried maintained more minerals and macronutrients than when it was shade-dried. In a similar vein, when compared to shade-dried *H. cannabinus* leaves, sun-dried leaves offered dietary allowance values for fiber, carbohydrates, protein, and minerals that were closer to the recommended dietary allowance (RDA). Therefore, sun drying is advised for *Hibiscus cannabinus* preservation and shelf life extension [3].

The typical or traditional method of employing sun radiation to dry agricultural products is to dry them in direct sunshine or in the open sun. The rate of dehydration considerably declined with time and was generally in the declining rate period. A falling-rate phase shows that the movement of moisture from the inside of the chip to its surface reduced the rate at which the banana stalk chip dried in the open sun [2].

Quality characteristics (Sensory characteristics)

Taste

When combined with water, curry leaf powder, ginger powder, and amla powder produced a variety of flavours, including a hint of sweetness, a strong ginger flavor, and a hint of earthiness from the dried curry leaf powder.

Aroma

The concoction smelled a little bit bitter from the powdered dried curry leaves, tangy from the amla, and spicy from the dry ginger powder. Overall the mixture of aroma was good and had a strong flavour.

Texture

Due to a good mixing of all three ingredients and the absence of coarse particles, the powder had a fine texture. After being fully mixed in a glass of water, the powder required a single filtering.

Conclusion

Amla, curry leaves, and ginger are nutritionally dense and pharmacologically potent plants widely used in traditional medicine. Rich in vitamins, minerals, antioxidants, and bioactive compounds, they exhibit remarkable therapeutic effects including anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, anti-cancer, cardioprotective, and neuroprotective properties. Their chemical and morphological characteristics make them valuable in both culinary and medicinal applications. Various drying techniques such as cabinet, sun, and shade drying improve shelf life while preserving nutritional quality. These plants also enhance sensory qualities when combined in food formulations. Overall, they play a significant role in promoting health and preventing lifestyle-related diseases, making them ideal functional food ingredients.

References

1. Abdelwahab, Siddig Ibrahim and Manal Mohamed Elhassan Taha. 2023. 'Global Research Trends of the Studies on *Murraya Koenigii* (L.) Spreng: A Scopus-Based Comprehensive Bibliometric Investigation (1965–2023)'. *Bulletin of the National Research Centre* 47(1).
2. Agbede, Oluseye Omotoso, Ifeoluwa Solomon Odewale, Oluwafunmilayo Abiola Aworanti, Solomon Oluyemi Alagbe, Oyetola Ogunkunle, and Opeyeolu Timothy Laseinde. 2023. 'Solar and Open Sun Drying of Untreated and Pretreated Banana Stalk Chips Biomass: A Sustainable Processing of Biomass Using Renewable Solar Energy'. *Discover Food* 3(1).
3. Agbemafle, Robert. 2020. 'Effects of Shade and Sun Drying on Nutrient Composition of *Hibiscus Cannabinus*'. *UDS International Journal of Development* 5(July):61–71.
4. Akshitha, H. J., K. Umesha, and D. Prasath. 2019. 'Morphological Characterization of Ginger (*Zingiber Officinale*) Using DUS Descriptors'. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences* 89(10):1744–47.
5. Alim, Md Abdul, Monirul Islam, Shirina Akter, Safa Maroua, Ashraful Alam, Md Esrafil, Md Azizul Haque, and Rokeya Begum. 2023. 'Optimization of Cabinet Drying Conditions for Dried Moringa Leaves by Response Surface Methodology'. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Research* 14(September):100794.

6. Anjali Yadav, Dr. Deepal Agarwal. 2024. 'INVESTIGATION ON CHEMICAL AND PHYTOCHEMICALS CONSTITUENTS OF PHYLLANTHUS EMBLICA'. 6.
7. Anjineyulu, Kothakota and Pandiselvam Ravi. 2016. 'Research Article A STUDY ON DRYING KINETICS OF INDIAN GOOSEBERRY – AONLA (Phyllanthus Emblica Linn.)'. *International Journal of Agriculture Sciences* 8(52):975–3710.
8. Al Arif, Mohammad Anam, Sunaryo Hadi Warsito, Mirni Lamid, Widya Paramita Lokapirnasari, Aswin Rafif Khairullah, Siti Rani Ayuti, Sugito, Intan Permatasari Hermawan, Oky Setyo Widodo, and Rakhi Gangil. 2024. 'Phytochemical Analysis of Curry Leaf Extract (Murraya Koenigii L.) as a Potential Animal Feed and Medicinal Ingredient'. *Pharmacognosy Journal* 16(2):471–77.
9. Avinash, Pawar Gayatri, Rafeeya Shams, Kshirod Kumar Dash, and Ayaz Mukarram Shaikh. 2024. 'Recent Insights into the Morphological, Nutritional and Phytochemical Properties of Indian Gooseberry (Phyllanthus Emblica) for the Development of Functional Foods'.
10. Ayustaningwarno, Fitriyono, Gemala Anjani, Azzahra Mutiara Ayu, and Vincenzo Fogliano. 2024. 'A Critical Review of Ginger's (Zingiber Officinale) Antioxidant, Anti-Inflammatory, and Immunomodulatory Activities'. *Frontiers in Nutrition* 11(June):1–16.
11. Balakrishnan, Rengasamy, Dhanraj Vijayaraja, Song-hee Jo, Palanivel Ganesan, In Su-kim, and Dong-kug Choi. 2020. 'Medicinal Profile, Phytochemistry, and Pharmacological Activities of Murraya Koenigii and Its Primary Bioactive Compounds'. *Antioxidants* 9:101.
12. Ballester, Pura, Begoña Cerdá, Raúl Arcusa, Javier Marhuenda, Karen Yamedjeu, and Pilar Zafrilla. 2022. 'Effect of Ginger on Inflammatory Diseases'. *Molecules* 27(21).
13. Bhusal, Dipika and Dharendra Pratap Thakur. 2021. 'Curry Leaf: A Review'. *Reviews in Food and Agriculture* 2(1):36–38.
14. Bishnoi, Sunil, Navnidhi Chhikara, Nisha Singhanian, and Aradhita Barman Ray. 2020. 'Effect of Cabinet Drying on Nutritional Quality and Drying Kinetics of Fenugreek Leaves (Trigonella Foenum-Graecum L.)'. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Research* 2(June):100072.
15. Bochar, Arti, Shankar Aher, and Dhanashri Jadhav. 2023. 'A REVIEW ARTICLE ON CURRY LEAF (Murraya Koenigii)'. *An International Open Access, Peer-Reviewed, Refereed Journal* 11(1):912–22.
16. Charmkar, Neeraj K. and Rajesh Singh. 2017. 'Emblica Officinalis Gaertn. (Amla): A Wonder Gift of Nature to Humans'. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences* 6(7):4267–80.
17. Chavan, Sahil, Siddhi Rikame, and Nilam Nile. 2025. 'From Tradition to Modern Medicine : Investigating the Pharmacological Benefits of Curry Leaves .' 3(2):1369–76.
18. Claudya, Rara Poetri, Helga Audelia Sugiaman, Salsabil Inas Labiba, Margaretha Pramesthi Utari, and Deni Gunawan. 2023. 'Science Midwifery The Therapeutic Effects of Ginger Extract on Gastrointestinal Disorders to Adults'. *Science Midwifery* 11(1):2721–9453.
19. Darekar, Shital Umakant, Dr. Sudarshan Narayan Nagrale, Dr. Vishal Bharat Babar, and Amit Pondkule. 2023. 'Review on Ginger: Chemical Constituents & Biological Effects'. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry* 12(6):267–71.
20. Das, Sanjib Kumar, Anuradha Das, Banamali Das, Purnendu Panda, G. C. Bhuyan, and Bipin Bihari Khuntia. 2017. ' Important Uses of Amalaki (Emblica Officinalis) in Indian System of Medicine with Pharmacological Evidence '. *Research Journal of Pharmacology and Pharmacodynamics* 9(4):202.
21. Devi S., Gupta E., Maurya N. K. 2020. 'Development of a Value Added Amla Product'. *International Archive of Applied Sciences and Technology* 11(2):90–93.
22. Fatema Pria, Firuz. 2019. '<I>Phyllanthus Emblica Linn.</I> (Amla) - A Natural Gift to Humans: An Overview'. *Journal of Diseases and Medicinal Plants* 5(1):1.

23. Gao, Jian Rui, Meng Yao Li, Zhe Yu Cheng, Xin Yu Liu, Hao Yang, Mao Ting Li, Rui Ying He, Qian Zhang, and Xu Hai Yang. 2024. 'Effects of Different Natural Drying Methods on Drying Characteristics'. *Agriculture (Switzerland)* 14(10).
24. Gul, Maryam, Zhi Wei Liu, Iahtisham-Ul-haq, Roshina Rabail, Fatima Faheem, Noman Walayat, Asad Nawaz, Muhammad Asim Shabbir, Paulo E. S. Munekata, José M. Lorenzo, and Rana Muhammad Aadil. 2022. 'Functional and Nutraceutical Significance of Amla (*Phyllanthus Emblica* L.): A Review'. *Antioxidants* 11(5):1–15.
25. Gupta, Vikas Kumar, Piyush Yadav, Vishal Prajapati, Suraj Maurya, and Manish Kumar. 2021. 'PHARMACOGNOSY OF GINGER OFFICINALE'. 9(1).
26. Hassan, Syeda Mona, Shahzad Sharif Mughal, Asma Aslam, Maryam Mushtaq, Muneeza Munir, Sumaira Pervez, Nageena Shabbir, Ali Raza Ayub, and Muhammad Farman. 2020. 'Emblca Officinalis (Amla): A Prospective Review On Distinctive Properties And Therapeutic Applications Of Amla Syeda'. *Biomedicine and Nursing* 6(2):22–30.
27. I.P. Ogbuewu, P.D. Jiwuba, C.T. Ezeokeke, M.C. Uchegbu, I. C. Okoli and M. U. Iloeje. 2022. 'EVALUATION OF PHYTOCHEMICAL AND NUTRITIONAL COMPOSITION OF GINGER RHIZOME POWDER'. *Journal of Spices and Aromatic Crops* (May):194–98.
28. Ikram, Ali, Waseem Khalid, Maryam Aziz, Muhammad Adnan Arif, Ravi Prakash Jha, Muhammad Zubair Khalid, Chasheen Fizza, Muhammad Zarnoor Mehmood, Muhammad Haseeb, Muhammad Abdul Rahim, Sadia Naeem, and Fatima Sultana. 2021. 'Nutritional and Biochemical Composition of Amla (*Emblca Officinalis*) and Its Therapeutic Impact: A Review'. *Acta Scientifci Nutritional Health* 5(2):153–60.
29. Jain, Akhil and Nidhi Garg. 2017. 'Therapeutic and Medicinal Uses of Amalaki: A Review'. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* 6(02):512–24.
30. Jain, P. K. and D. Das. 2016. 'Pharmacognostic Comparison of *Bacopa Monnieri*, *Cyperus Rotundus*, and *Emblca Officinalis*'. *Innovare Journal of Ayurvedic Sciences* 4(4):16–26.
31. Kausar, Tahreem, Sadaf Anwar, Entesar Hanan, Mifftha Yaseen, Shimaa M. H. Aboelnaga, and Z. R. Azaz Ahmad Azad. 2021. 'Therapeutic Role of Ginger (*Zingiber Officinale*) - A Review'. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research International* 33:9–16.
32. Kiyama, Ryoiti. 2020. 'Nutritional Implications of Ginger: Chemistry, Biological Activities and Signaling Pathways'. *Journal of Nutritional Biochemistry* 86:108486.
33. Krushi Vidyapeeth, Marathwada, India HM Syed Professor, and Naik Marathwada Krushi Vidyapeeth. 2020. 'Effect of Different Drying Treatment on Composition, Nutritional and Phytochemical Content of Curry Leaves Salve RV, Syed HM, More SG and Shinde EM'. ~ 584 ~ *The Pharma Innovation Journal* 9(7):584–89.
34. Kulkarni, Kaushik Vilas and Shrishail M. Ghurghure. 2018. 'Indian Gooseberry (*Emblca Officinalis*): Complete Pharmacognosy Review'. *International Journal of Chemistry Studies* 2(2):5–11.
35. Kumar, Rahul, Shifali Gupta, Paranjeet Kaur, and Sanjeev Kumar Sahu. 2024. 'Exploring the Potential of Curry Leaves for Their Therapeutic Action'. *BIO Web of Conferences* 86:1–10.
36. Kumari, Beena and Correspondence Beena Kumari. 2018. 'Taxonomy and Ethnobotany of *Murraya Koenigii* (L.) Spreng: An Exotic Shrub in Rohilkhand Region of Uttar Pradesh'. ~ 123 ~ *Journal of Medicinal Plants Studies* 6(4):123–25.
37. Kumari, Meenakshi and S. S. Solankey Manoj Kumar. 2020. 'Chapter 20 *Zingiber Officinale* Roscoe : Ginger'. (October).
38. Lal, Manohar and Navjot Kaur. 2019. 'Effect of Processing on Nutritional and Anti-Nutritional Composition of Curry Leaves (*Murraya Koenigii*)'. *International Journal of Home Science* 5(3):186–90.
39. Liu, Huanfang, Chelsea D. Specht, Tong Zhao, and Jingping Liao. 2020. 'Morphological Anatomy of Leaf and Rhizome in *Zingiber Officinale* Roscoe, with Emphasis on Secretory Structures'. *HortScience* 55(2):204–7.

40. Mankar, S. ..., M. S. Bhosale, Mohini Shelke, and Pankaj Sonawane. 2021. 'A Review on *Murraya Koenigii*: For Hair Growth Promoter'. *Research Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry* 13(1):39–43.
41. Meher, Jagamohan, M. Geethu, G. Kalusuraman, and R. S. Maheswari. 2024. 'A Comprehensive Review on the Morphology, Chemistry, and Multifaceted Applications of Curry Leaves'. 6(14).
42. Mishra, Aradhana and Deoraj Sharma. 2023. 'Multiple Health Benefits of Amla in Our Day-to-Day Life'. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Life Science* 4(2):60–68.
43. Mittal, Jitendra. 2017. 'Curry Leaf (*Murraya Koenigii*): A Spice with Medicinal Property'. *MOJ Biology and Medicine* 2(3).
44. Nakhale, Swati, Souvik Tewari, and Sudhakara Rao. 2021. 'Potential Health Benefits of Amla (*Phyllanthus Emblica*): A Review'. *Journal of Science and Technology* 06(01):83–87.
45. Namrata, Kumari, Kavita Verma, Sunita Kushwah, Swapnil Bharti, Sri Priya Das, Anup Kumar Singh, and Prem Prakash Gautam. 2023. 'Comparative Study On Shade Drying, Sun Drying And Direct Solar Drying Of Mint Leaves'. *Agriculture Association of Textile Chemical and Critical Reviews Journal* 11(4):246–50.
46. Nandy, Shouvik and Sattwik Das. 2023. 'Unveiling the Diverse Medicinal Properties of *Murraya Koenigii*'. *Sciences of Phytochemistry* 2(2):107–26.
47. Nigam, Lata. 2023. 'A Review on Medicinal Benefits of Curry Leaves'. *Journal of Advancement in Pharmacognosy* 3(1):2023.
48. Pandey, Kajal, Manvi Arora, and Sonam Chawla. 2022. 'Recent Perspectives on the Medicinal Potential of Plant-Based Adaptogens'. *Phytopharmaceuticals and Biotechnology of Herbal Plants* 267–79.
49. Prananda, Arya Tjipta, Aminah Dalimunthe, Urip Harahap, Yogi Simanjuntak, Epina Peronika, Natasya Elsa Karosekali, Poppy Anjelisa Zaitun Hasibuan, Rony Abdi Syahputra, Putri Cahaya Situmorang, and Fahrul Nurkolis. 2023. 'Phyllanthus Emblica: A Comprehensive Review of Its Phytochemical Composition and Pharmacological Properties'. *Frontiers in Pharmacology* 14(October):1–20.
50. Prasad, Sahdeo and Amit K. Tyagi. 2015. 'Ginger and Its Constituents: Role in Prevention and Treatment of Gastrointestinal Cancer'. *Gastroenterology Research and Practice* 2015.
51. Precoppe, Marcelo, Serm Janjai, Busarakorn Mahayothee, and Joachim Müller. 2015. 'Batch Uniformity and Energy Efficiency Improvements on a Cabinet Dryer Suitable for Smallholder Farmers'. *Journal of Food Science and Technology* 52(8):4819–29.
52. Roshanak, Sahar, Mehdi Rahimmalek, and Sayed Amir Hossein Goli. 2016. 'Evaluation of Seven Different Drying Treatments in Respect to Total Flavonoid, Phenolic, Vitamin C Content, Chlorophyll, Antioxidant Activity and Color of Green Tea (*Camellia Sinensis* or *C. Assamica*) Leaves'. *Journal of Food Science and Technology* 53(1):721–29.
53. Rungsung, Wungsem, Sreya Dutta, Dharendra Nath Mondal, and Jayram Hazra. 2014. 'Pharmacognostical Characterization on the Rhizome of Ginger'. *Res. J. Pharmacognosy & Phytochem* 6(June):88–91.
54. S. G. Pawar, S. G. Phalphe and K. R. Biyani. 2024. 'A REVIEW ON THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF AMLA DRUG (*EMBLICA OFFICINALIS*)'. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development* 6(1):67–70.
55. Shalaby, Emad A., Sanaa M. M. Shanab, Rehab M. Hafez, and Abeer E. El-Ansary. 2023. 'Chemical Constituents and Biological Activities of Different Extracts from Ginger Plant (*Zingiber Officinale*)'. *Chemical and Biological Technologies in Agriculture* 10(1):1–17.

56. Shams, Rafeeya, Jagmohan Singh, Kshirod K. Dash, and Aamir Hussain Dar. 2022. 'Comparative Study of Freeze Drying and Cabinet Drying of Button Mushroom'. *Applied Food Research* 2(1):100084.
57. Sharma, Yogeshwar. 2017. 'Ginger (Zingiber Officinale)-An Elixir of Life a Review'. *The Pharma Innovation Journal* 6(11):22-27.
58. Shaukat, Muhammad Nouman, Akmal Nazir, and Biagio Fallico. 2023. 'Ginger Bioactives: A Comprehensive Review of Health Benefits and Potential Food Applications'. *Antioxidants* 12(11):1-26.
59. Shrivastava, Sanjana, Jaspreet Kaur, Mahrukh Mehraj, Fathima Feroz, Jyoti Chawla, and Surbhi Kumari. 2022. 'The Pharma Innovation Journal 2022; 11(6): 06-16 Emblica Officinalis (Amla): A Comprehensive Review of the Miracle Berry'. *The Pharma Innovation Journal* 11(6):6-16.
60. Singh, Jyotsana, Ifra Nigar, Deep Kumar, Shalabh Sharma, Harsh Kumar, and Damini Rani. 2024. 'Health Benefits of Ginger : A Review'. 10(2):49-55.
61. Singh, Suman and Sandhya Madan Mohan Head. 2014. 'CURRY LEAVES (Murraya Koenigii Linn. Sprengal)-A MIRACLE PLANT'. *Indian J.Sci.Res* 4(1):46-52.
62. Sonkar, Nitin, Deependra Rajoriya, R. Chetana, and K. Venkatesh Murthy. 2020. 'Effect of Cultivars, Pretreatment and Drying on Physicochemical Properties of Amla (Emblica Officinalis) Gratings'. *Journal of Food Science and Technology* 57(3):980-92.
63. Sunmola, T. A. *. and K. T. Aheemen. 2021. 'The Proximate Composition, Antinutritional Factors and Selected Minerals in Yellow and White Ginger (Zingiber Officinale) and Local Turmeric (Curcuma Longa)'. *Malaysian Society of Animal Production* 24(2):1-14.
64. Suthar, Priyanka, Satish Kumar, Vikas Kumar, Devina Vaidya, Ajay Sharma, and Ajit Sharma. 2022. 'Murraya Koenigii (L.) Spreng: Speculative Ethnobotanical Perspectives of Ubiquitous Herb with Versatile Nutra/Functional Properties'. *South African Journal of Botany* 145:111-34.
65. Unuofin, Jeremiah Oshiomame, Nelisiwe Prenate Masuku, Oluwatomiwa Kehinde Paimo, and Sogolo Lucky Lebelo. 2021. 'Ginger from Farmyard to Town: Nutritional and Pharmacological Applications'. *Frontiers in Pharmacology* 12(November).
66. Varma, Kanika and Mamta Parnami. 2019. 'Nutritional Composition of Dried Curry Leaf Powder (Murraya Koenigii)'. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)* 6(6):409-12.
67. Wang, Weiyue, Zenghao Yan, Hongliang Yao, Peibo Li, Wei Peng, Weiwei Su, and Yonggang Wang. 2021. 'Comparison of Traditional and Novel Drying Techniques and Its Effect on Quality of Fruits, Vegetables and Aromatic Herbs'. *Separation Science and Technology (Philadelphia)* 56(10):1710-20.
68. Yurleni and Adriani. 2021. 'Antioxidant Activity and Bioactive Components of Curry Leaves (Murraya Koenigii) to Lower Red Meat Cholesterol: Morphological, Chemical Content Curry Leaves and Putrefaction Test of Meat '. *Proceedings of the 3rd Green Development International Conference (GDIC 2020)* 205(Gdic 2020):114-19.